

Harmful Algae News

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Rapid response to a massive marine mammal stranding event associated with domoic acid poisoning in central to southern California

6-5-2023 | Probability of Particulate Domoic Acid > 500 ng L⁻¹

Fig. 1: **a)** NOAA CoastWatch California-Harmful Algae Risk Mapping (C-HARM) system prediction of pDA risk (red = higher risk) on 9 June 2023; C-HARM tracked the nexus of the DA event from SLO to San Diego Counties. SCCOOS Cal-HABMAP and CA Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) Network stations are labeled with a circle and IFCB icon. **b)** (foreground) CSLs displaying signs of domoic acid poisoning and (background) a deceased long-beaked common dolphin. Credit: CIMWI; **c)** beached long-beaked common dolphin. Credit: CIMWI.

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Blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* are an almost annual occurrence in the California Current System [1, 2]. The last two years have seen sizable blooms with significant marine mammal impacts, but what has made 2023 stand out is the duration of the late spring-early summer bloom and the huge number of marine mammal strandings. California sea lions (CSL, *Zalophus californianus*) are well-known sentinels of domoic acid (DA) events, usually exhibiting distinctive behavioral signs of DA exposure [3,4]. Thus, the first few strandings of symptomatic CSLs at the end of May alerted marine mammal stranding response organizations to an impending problem. Only one week later, it was becoming clear that the dramatic increase in live and dead stranded CSLs and common dolphins (*Delphinus delphis*) throughout the Santa Barbara Channel region was likely due to DA poisoning. The tell-tale signs of the neurotoxin were prevalent in CSLs and other pinnipeds along popular beaches – disorientation, twitching, seizures, erratic behavior – as the event expanded to encompass the region from San Luis Obispo (SLO) County in central California to San Diego County in southern California over the next few weeks (Fig. 1). In fact, many animals displayed extreme aggression with at least seven reports of attacks, some serious, on beachgoers in the months of June and July ([5], CIMWI and PMMC communications).

The California Harmful Algal Bloom Monitoring and Alert Program (Cal-HABMAP) supported by the Southern California Coastal Ocean Observing System (SCCOOS) and the Central and Northern California Ocean Observing System (CeNCOOS) conducts weekly sampling at almost ten nearshore sites throughout California (Fig. 1), with a focus on enumerating the most problematic HAB taxa and analyzing samples in the laboratory for DA [6]. Cell abundance data are typically shared via the HABMAP email listserv a few weeks before toxin data become available in order to alert the community of potential bloom activity. While all the sites except Scripps Pier recorded a dramatic uptick in *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. in mid-to-late May, only a few of those sites reported bloom levels of the larger, more toxigenic ‘seriata’ size class and those trends were not long-

lasting, leading the HABMAP community to conjecture a possible ephemeral, nearshore bloom that rapidly advected offshore or a primarily offshore origin to the marine mammals DA-poisoning cases. The newly established California Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) Network operates robotic microscopes at Stearns Wharf (Santa Barbara), Newport Beach Pier (Orange County), and Scripps Pier (San Diego) for high-frequency, real-time plankton imagery and identification (Fig. 1), which would have been an ideal platform for evaluating nearshore dynamics. Unfortunately,

three out of four IFCBs in the region were undergoing maintenance as this bloom developed. HABMAP sampling did capture a resurgence of bloom levels of the ‘seriata’ size class cells in the second half of June at Monterey Wharf (southern Monterey Bay), Cal Poly Pier (SLO), Stearns Wharf, and Santa Monica Pier (Los Angeles), suggesting a delay in onshore movement of the bloom or even a possible cycle of offshore advection followed by vertical delivery of the *Pseudo-nitzschia* populations onto the shelf via upwelling processes (Fig. 2). In fact, April-May values of the Biological-

Fig. 2: Measurements from weekly California Harmful Algal Bloom Monitoring and Alert Program (Cal-HABMAP) sampling from May to July 2023 for **a)** particulate domoic acid (pDA) concentration (ng mL^{-1}); **b)** *Pseudo-nitzschia* ‘seriata’ size class abundance (cells L^{-1}) and **c)** *Pseudo-nitzschia* ‘delicatissima’ size class abundance (cells L^{-1}). The dashed line on *Pseudo-nitzschia* plots demarcates the $10,000 \text{ cells L}^{-1}$ ‘bloom’ operational threshold. Credit: SCCOOS.

ly Effective Upwelling Transport Index (BEUTI; <https://mjacox.com/upwelling-indices/>) were anomalously high for central California the last two years, while hovering around average for southern California. This index tells us how much nitrate was likely available for primary production and is a strong indicator of bloom potential, suggesting that conditions in spring 2023 were conducive to supporting a prolonged bloom scenario.

The only synoptic, real-time view of the bloom available to researchers and the public was the California Harmful Algae Risk Mapping (C-HARM) System, a 1-3-day forecast produced by NOAA CoastWatch that predicts both the probability of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. blooms (above 10,000 cells L⁻¹) and high-DA surface water (>500 ng L⁻¹) at a 4-km horizontal resolution throughout coastal California [7]. C-HARM predictions homed in on a large swath of the central to southern California coast as an extreme hot spot for DA risk, highlighting the offshore potential for DA production and animal exposure (Fig 1). C-HARM predictions of DA risk have been shown to correlate well with CSL stranding records, but they are not well-suited for predicting DA risk in the most nearshore zones [7]. The HABMAP toxin data were not available until early July when they eventually revealed that there were elevated DA concentrations at Cal Poly Pier as early as May 15th followed by “event” levels of DA by June 5th, but by that date, the *Pseudo-nitzschia* population had shifted from the ‘seriata’ size class to the smaller, less toxic “delicatissima” size class (Fig. 2). This decoupling between cell densities and toxin concentration is a perennial struggle for predicting DA. The biological complexity related to the subtle differences in species, strains, the ratio of particulate to dissolved toxin, and variability in coastal to pelagic toxin vectors all confound our understanding of DA production and food web transfer.

These complexities are apparent when comparing the last two major events in our region. The CSL stranding numbers from the August 2022 DA event last summer were half those of 2023 (~500 vs. >1,000 animals) despite high DA in the water column in 2022 (J. Smith, unpublished data). For dolphin strandings, this year reached

well over 100 cases as compared with ~30 in 2022, with many more pregnant females affected this year relative to other years. In addition, 10 live dolphin strandings were reported this year, which is rather rare. In terms of toxicity, the 2022 event resulted in some of the highest DA concentrations measured in animals – 500,000 ng/g in northern fur seal (*Callorhinus ursinus*) feces (R. Kudela, unpublished results). This year, dozens of dolphin samples collected by the Channel Islands Cetacean Research Unit (CICRU) and analyzed by the Northwest Fisheries Science Center’s Wildlife Algal-Toxins Research and Response Network (NWFSC/WARRN-West, K. Lefebvre unpublished results) are yielding similar results, with a high of 296,538 ng/g DA in feces from a dolphin collected from Ventura County on 19 June 2023 and many others above 100,000 ng/g. On the human exposure side, there were no new recreational shellfish advisories associated with Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) during the 2022 DA event. In 2023, the California Department of Public Health issued ASP advisories for bivalves that lagged shore station DA spikes and marine mammal strandings by almost a month, with the first alert posted on June 16th for Santa Barbara County. Interestingly, subsequent shellfish advisories issued for SLO and San Mateo Counties were due to the threat of Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (*Alexandrium/saxitoxin*), not in relation to ASP. Given that the highest nearshore DA measured as part of HABMAP was at Cal Poly Pier, it is difficult to explain why no ASP advisory was ever issued for SLO County, although an annual mandatory quarantine for recreational mussel harvests is in place statewide to guard against ASP from May - October. In sum, there is 1) limited information on the conditions supporting DA bioaccumulation and depuration across a suite of bivalve taxa, 2) very little routine offshore sampling, and 3) significant seasonal and interannual variability in environmental conditions that trigger DA production [8, 9]. These remain knowledge and observing gaps for the community. Moreover, mammal and seabird life histories and foraging patterns in conjunction with toxic prey behavior [10] create a multi-dimensional tapestry that currently eludes forecasts of food web impacts.

Given this challenge to predict when and where animals will be most affected by a phycotoxin like DA, first responders at Marine Mammal Stranding Network (MMSN) organizations are often caught off-guard when strandings increase exponentially over the course of one week. When multiple MMSN partners are required to respond simultaneously, not only are volunteer networks strained but coordination between organizations becomes critical. The research community is accustomed to acting quickly to seek science funding, such as the NOAA NCCOS MERHAB Event Response opportunity. Indeed, co-authors have been awarded modest funding in both 2022 and 2023 to work with partners to collect offshore water samples, comprehensively characterize animal tissue toxicity and variability, and improve communication and data sharing across the marine mammal stranding network. Ships-of-opportunity are an essential component of event response when offshore blooms occur, with largely in-kind assistance from multiple non-governmental organizations providing our main characterization of offshore conditions. SCCOOS staff worked with the team to communicate daily with the MMSN, collating C-HARM predictions, news articles, and incoming data from the field into a web application. While rapid response funding is critical for assessing the causes and impacts of stranding events, it is not intended to directly improve staffing, supply, and volunteer shortages for response, rescue, and research activities, and the agencies and responders are also often underfunded to rapidly communicate within the network, other partners, and the general public. This highlights critical structural needs for improving MMSN efficacy through more sustained support and underscores the disconnect between the research community’s efforts to understand bloom ecology and predictability and the sometimes loosely connected array of institutions and municipalities tasked with safeguarding protected marine life populations and the public.

What the California HAB response community has learned from two consecutive years with large marine mammal stranding events associated with DA poisoning is that coordination is not just necessary but must be comprehen-

sive, multi-agency, and transdisciplinary. A codified pipeline for communications and data distribution during DA events that is developed during non-event periods, and ideally refined during smaller events, is desperately needed for the California HAB, marine animal, and human health communities to more effectively address animal welfare and public safety concerns, as well as research priorities during future HAB events.

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NEW BOOK!

Marine benthic dinoflagellates – their relevance for science and society

By Mona Hoppenrath, Nicolas Chomérat, Takeo Horiguchi, Shauna A. Murray & Lesley Rhodes

This book is the most comprehensive summary of our knowledge of benthic dinoflagellate species, including a compilation of their toxins.

More information to be found [here](#)

Northward expansion of the Atlantic waters may lead to increased presence of HAB species in the western Barents Sea

Fig. 1. Study region of the western Barents Sea with diagram of circulations [2] being superimposed on the topographical map (Yellow dashed line cycles indicate major areas of presence of HAB species).

The Barents Sea (BS) is one of the most productive shelf seas in the pan-Arctic region, with great wild-capture fisheries of cod, haddock and capelin [1] along with large populations of marine mammals and seabirds. Here we present an overview of Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) taxa observed in a suite of research cruises in the western BS (Fig. 1) as a baseline for the monitoring of marine HABs in this region of the Arctic.

Two multidisciplinary cruises were carried out in summer 2017 (30th Jun – 8th Aug) and 2018 (11th Jun to 6th Jul). Discrete water samples of phytoplankton were collected at the surface, sub-surface (chlorophyll maximum) and deeper waters (1% of the surface irradiance) using a multi-sensor CTD sampler. After 24 h settling of the Lugol's fixed subsamples in Utermöhl chambers [3], identification and enumeration of targeted HAB species were undertaken with an inverted light microscope.

A total of 85 taxa were observed over the two cruises, of which 24 taxa were harmful, with 15 taxa being potentially toxic. Four taxa (*Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*, *Pseudo-nitzschia delicatissima* type and *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* type cells; Fig. 2) were observed with cell abundances above typical shellfish safety bloom thresholds of 40 cells L⁻¹, 100 cells L⁻¹ and 5 × 10⁴ cell L⁻¹ [4]. Four other taxa (*Azadinium*, *Heterocapsa*, *Karlodinium* and *Prorocentrum cordatum*; Fig. 3) were observed, but with cell abundances below bloom values reported elsewhere [5, 6, 7].

Domoic acid producing *P. delicatissima* and *P. seriata* groups were observed to be widely distributed in the western BS from the Barents Sea Opening (BSO) across the BS shelf to the shelf break near Nansen Basin (Fig. 2e, f, g, h). The mean abundances of the *P. delicatissima* group reached up to 3.4 × 10⁴ cells/L (maximum of 3.3 × 10⁵ cells/L) and

8.7 × 10³ cells/L (maximum of 4.6 × 10⁴ cells/L) from all of the samples collected during summer 2017 and 2018, accounting for 94.1% and 89.0% of the total *Pseudo-nitzschia* abundances respectively. A large bloom (>5 × 10⁴ cells/L) of the *P. seriata* group was recorded from one sample in the southern BSO in summer 2017 (Fig. 2g), with cell abundance reaching 1.6 × 10⁵ cells/L. Although *P. seriata* group blooms were not detected in summer 2018 (Fig. 2h), relatively high abundances of this group were widely distributed far into the north across the BS shelf, probably due to the low sea ice extent (Fig. 1).

The presence of saxitoxin producing *Alexandrium* was very common in summer phytoplankton assemblages of the western BS (Fig. 2a, b), with frequency of blooms (>40 cells/L) of 36.0% and 37.5%, and maxima of 1.3 × 10³ cells/L and 260 cells/L in summer 2017 and 2018 respectively. The okadaic acid producing *Dinophysis* also regularly presented in summer seawaters of the western BS (Fig. 2c, d), with bloom abundances (>100 cells/L) of 400 cells/L and 120 cells/L being recorded in the same location (east of Spitsbergen) of summer 2017 and 2018.

Of the other potentially harmful dinoflagellates observed (Fig. 3), the highest abundances of *P. cordatum* reached up to 3.5 × 10⁴ cells/L (mean of 1.7 × 10³ cells/L) and 4.6 × 10³ cells/L (mean of 411 cells/L) in the waters southwest of Svalbard (Fig. 3g) and east of Spitsbergen (Fig. 3h) in summer 2017 and 2018 respectively. *Azadinium* (Fig. 3a, b), *Heterocapsa* (Fig. 3c, d) and *Karlodinium* (Fig. 3e, f) also regularly presented in the samples, with maxima of 1.4 × 10³ cells/L, 2.4 × 10³ cells/L and 560 cells/L in summer 2017, and 1.2 × 10³ cells/L, 700 cells/L and 620 cells/L in summer 2018 respectively.

There were four major areas of presence of HAB species in the western BS (Fig. 1). Besides the area in the southern BSO, with a high risk of the toxic diatom *P. seriata* group, there were also three major areas (east of Spitsbergen, southwest of Svalbard and north of White Island) at high risk of toxic dinoflagellates. It is obvious that these four areas were closely associated with the northward expansion of the Atlantic waters [2] deriving from the North Cape Current, the West Spitsbergen Current

Fig. 2. Distributions of major HAB taxa (cell abundances above bloom thresholds) in the western Barents Sea in summer 2017 and 2018 (Diamonds display the maximum abundance that occurred in the sampling layers).

Fig. 3. Distributions of major HAB taxa (cell abundances below reported bloom values) in the western Barents Sea in summer 2017 and 2018 (Diamonds display the maximum abundance that occurred in the sampling layers).

and the Atlantic water boundary current. The encroaching warm and saline Atlantic waters in the BS and the Arctic provided an hospitable environment for the growth and persistence of those HAB taxa. Interestingly, some dinoflagellates (e.g. *P. cordatum*) recorded may behave mixotrophically [8] and could become an important component of the phytoplankton community in late summer or early autumn when the diatom cells began to die and sink out of the surface water allowing greater amounts of lights through.

The Arctic phytoplankton are experiencing borealization [9], a transition from polar to temperate regime. It is foreseeable that the presence of HAB species in the BS will continue increasing in light of the receding sea ice and northward expansion of the Atlantic waters. However, large uncertainty still remains about whether these species bloom locally or are being transferred from southern coastal waters. Field *in situ* evidence has been reported from the Alaskan Arctic waters [10], where the blooms of *Alexandrium* originated from both the transport by temperate Pacific waters and the local germination of resting cysts. Previous field investigation on dinocysts in the western BS [11] revealed the predominance of *Protoceratium reticulatum* cysts in the Atlantic-water influenced surface sediments. Although this yessotoxin producer presented in the waters east of Spitsbergen (summer 2017) and north of White Island (summer 2018), the cell abundances were quiet low (maximum of 40 cells/L) in the total communities.

HAB species, non-toxic or toxic, may lead to seawater discoloration, anoxia,

mucilage or toxicity. Shellfish poisoning (of humans and marine mammals) and fish-kill events caused by HAB species are of growing concern worldwide. In the context of a warming ocean, 'Will the Arctic seas be a new HABs hotspot?' is still a challenging question. Warming of Arctic waters, driven by both atmospheric heating and southern water inflows, may fundamentally altered the ecophysiological characteristics of those HAB species (being transferred or germinating from cysts locally), making them more suitable for a 'temperate state' Arctic environment. This intrusion of HAB species to the Arctic phytoplankton may lead to cascading effect within the food webs and the entire ecosystem, and may generate potentially far-reaching ramifications to human and animal health through consumption of toxin accumulated seafood from wild fisheries, and from aquaculture should it become more established in the Arctic.

Increasing needs for field observations on these HAB species and toxins (including new or emerging) in the Arctic Seas are urgent, even though such campaigns are routinely performed due to logistic difficulties and lack of infrastructure. New monitoring tools, such as AUVs mounted with autonomous cell counters may offer the potential to capture the timing and distributions of these HABs, especially in the late summer or early autumn when dinoflagellates flourish and become dominant in the phytoplankton communities. In short, long-term field studies and modeling efforts should be undertaken now and in the future, to ensure a healthy Arctic marine ecosystem which sup-

ports services for the well-being of residents and indigenous people in the pan-Arctic region in a fluctuating climate.

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High-Biomass Harmful Algal Blooms (HB-HAB) in the Chilean Fjords System: *Prorocentrum micans*

Fig. 1. Bloom of *Prorocentrum micans* in Reloncavi Sound, NW Patagonia, Chile. A) Location of the bloom; B) Copernicus Sentinel-2 Satellite image showing the distribution of Chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) in Reloncavi Sound, during the bloom; C) Aerial image of the bloom, showing extensive brown coloration of the surface layer of the sound.

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) are recurrent in Patagonian Fjord System. Although High-Biomass-HABs (HB-HABs) have socio-economic repercussions, most studies have focused on toxin-producing microalgae [1]. Two species that form HB-HABs are *Lepidodinium chlorophorum* and *Prorocentrum micans*, dinoflagellates associated with events commonly called “green tides” and “brown tides”, respectively. Both species have been recorded in NW Patagonia where they have formed intense surface blooms with increasing frequency over the last years [2].

During the summer of 2022, an in-

tense HB-HAB formed by the dinoflagellate *P. micans* occurred in NW Chilean Patagonia. Intense brown spots visible on the water surface and a strong ‘gas’ odour were reported at the end of February in the Reloncavi Sound and Ancud Gulf (Fig. 1). The Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite images showed a colour change corresponding to the presence of intense brown patches on February 22 in the area, which was confirmed by the high chlorophyll *a* concentration (up to $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; Fig. 1B) recorded.

Phytoplankton data from the salmon farming monitoring programme at Reloncavi Sound showed an intense

bloom of *P. micans* from February 10 to March 10, 2022. The highest cell density of *P. micans* occurred on February 24, with values $> 8.3 \times 10^3$ cells mL^{-1} measured at the surface (Fig. 2A). Oceanographic conditions recorded at the i-mar oceanographic buoy, located at the center of the Reloncavi Sound, were related to the temporal variability of *P. micans* cell densities through a T-S diagram showing a marked preference for conditions of narrow, high salinity ranges that fluctuated between 28 and 31 psu (Fig. 2B). Likewise, the highest densities were also recorded with high temperature values ($16.5 - 19^\circ\text{C}$).

Microphytoplankton analysis of samples water collected on February 17, 2022 close to the mouth of Reloncavi Fjord showed a phytoplankton diversity of 35 species. Nevertheless, the phytoplankton community was dominated only by two species, the diatom *Leptocylindrus danicus* ($>50.9\%$) and the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans* (41.9%), with surface cell maxima of $1,195$ cells mL^{-1} and 983 cells mL^{-1} , respectively (Fig. 3A). These high cell densities were consistent with a high chlorophyll *a* (chl-*a*) signal in the first 5 m of depth ($\sim 28 \mu\text{g chl-}a \text{ L}^{-1}$), associated with intense thermohaline stratification (Fig. 3B).

One of the environmental variables that has been described as a trigger for this type of event corresponds to the increase in the concentration of nutrients in the water column, mainly ammonium from the degradation of organic matter [3]. The increased N in coastal ecosystems has been driven globally by the intensification of aquaculture, massive land transformation, agriculture, and sewage. Until now, no massive mortalities of farmed salmon associated with HB-HAB of *P. micans* have been reported in Southern Chile. Nevertheless, the presence of intense areas of visible water discoloration in coastal areas of Reloncavi Sound, alongside the presence of an intense fetid odour, similar to decomposing organic matter reported by many residents in different localities in the area during the event, triggered a public alarm in the local communities, mainly in Puerto Montt city. This fetid odour is most likely linked to the emission of dimethyl sulfide gas or DMS which is the result of the decomposition of the dimethyl-sulfoniopropionate

Fig. 2. Cell densities of *Prorocentrum micans* and their occurrence with temperature and salinity. A) Cell densities of *P. micans*, before, during and after the bloom; B) Cell densities of *P. micans* as functions of surface water temperature and salinity.

Fig. 3. Phytoplankton assemblage during the bloom of *Prorocentrum micans* at different water column depth (0–50 m), and vertical profile of temperature, salinity and Chlorophyll a in the water column (0–25 m).

(DMSP) produced by the bloom of *P. micans*, following grazing by higher trophic levels and lysis by microbes [4-5].

Recently, Diaz et al. [6] described HB-HAB events in Chilean Patagonia that are associated with dry summers and high solar radiation. Thus, consid-

ering the climatic trend observed in recent decades and the future projections for this area, the risk of increased occurrence and intensity of HB-HAB may increase. Consequently, the lack of knowledge about the basic aspects of the biology and behavior of both spe-

cies (*L. chlorophorum* and *P. micans*) in coastal waters of southern Chile's fjord systems, as well as the critical levels (cell density) at which they begin to induce negative impacts on both the regional aquaculture industry and the public health, has made it difficult to implement timely management measures that would allow the mitigation of their negative impacts.

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Identification of Caribbean ciguatoxins from benthic dinoflagellates advances knowledge on toxin chemistry and analysis

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) is a serious food-borne illness caused by the consumption of seafood from endemic tropical and sub-tropical regions, including the Pacific, Atlantic and Indian Oceans, and the Caribbean Sea, that contain highly toxic ciguatoxins (CTXs) that are present at very low levels [1]. Ciguatoxins are produced by *Gambierdiscus* spp. and transferred through the marine food web following consumption by reef herbivores. Microalgal species responsible for the production of CTXs in the Pacific Ocean (P-CTXs) were identified in the last decades of the 20th century, facilitating the production and purification of P-CTXs from culture, analytical method development, and leading a deeper understanding of the metabolism, trophic transfer, and toxicology of P-CTXs[2, 3].

Ciguatera poisoning in the Caribbean is associated with a class of CTXs that were initially isolated and identified in fish from the region. Lewis *et al.* first identified Caribbean CTX-1 (CCTX1) in the late 1990s[4]. Since that time, no additional C-CTXs were definitively identified, nor had an algal source of C-CTXs been confirmed with certainty, although *Gambierdiscus* spp. were suspected to be involved based on *in vitro* bioassays. It has since been shown that C-CTXs occur in fish not only in the Caribbean Sea, but throughout the tropical Atlantic Ocean and even in the Mediterranean Sea[5]. However, the lack of an identified algal source, and the difficulty of producing sufficient purified C-CTXs from fish, has impeded progress on the toxicology, analytical chemistry, and ecological risk assessments of this toxin group, and has hindered the development of effective mitigation strategies for CP management in these regions.

In an attempt to address these issues, an international collaborative project, CiguaPIRE, was initiated in 2017 funded by the US National Science Foundation with parallel support from the Norwegian Research Council,

Center for the Environment, Aquaculture and Fisheries Sciences (UK), and the National Research Council of Canada[6]. The project includes global partners from the US, UK, Canada, Norway, and Australia, along with partnerships with a large group of both sovereign island nations and dependent island territories throughout the Caribbean and Western Atlantic. The overall objectives of this global initiative were to examine the dynamics and persistence of toxigenic benthic dinoflagellates and their metabolites in reefs around the globe to better understand the production and fate of C-CTXs. To enable this, it was necessary to develop improved analytical and purification methods for

CTXs to allow identification and sensitive detection of an array of novel toxins in algae, invertebrates, and fish.

The initial focus of chemical research within CiguaPIRE included isolation of C-CTX1 from fish, and use of this semi-purified material for method development and *in vitro* metabolism studies that led to the identification of novel glucuronides of C-CTX1 [7]. The availability of C-CTX1 also led to the confirmation of the metabolites C-CTX3 and C-CTX4 as the C-56 reduction products of C-CTX1, through a series of chemical transformations combined with LC-HRMS comparisons with extracts from naturally contaminated fish [8]. Furthermore, the production of isotopically labelled C-CTX1[9], and development of methods for selective boronate extraction of C-CTXs (and a range of P-CTXs) from fish extracts, hold promise for improving analysis time while reducing the impacts of potential matrix effects and interferences[10].

The improved LC-HRMS method

Fig. 1. Structures of the new algal precursor, C-CTX5, and its relationship to C-CTX1 and C-CTX3/4 previously identified in fish.

Fig. 2. Toxin content per cell (peak area per cell) grown in L1 medium at a salinity of 35‰ over 32-days (error bars: standard deviation of three culture replicates). Inset: Light microscopy image of *Gambierdiscus silvae* cells in culture ($\times 400$ magnification)

was used to identify a putative C-CTX1 analogue, named C-CTX5 (Fig. 1), in established cultures of *Gambierdiscus silvae* and *G. caribaeus* from the Caribbean Sea [11]. The chemical transformation and isotopic labelling procedures developed in the project for C-CTX1 and C-CTX3/4 were applied to C-CTX5 to unambiguously show that it was 3-oxoC-CTX1. It was then demonstrated that C-CTX5 was biotransformed to C-CTX1 by fish liver microsomes, showing that it is a precursor to the C-CTX1 found in fish. In a semiquantitative study, C-CTX5 was shown to have slightly lower ciguatoxin-like activity than C-CTX1 in an *in vitro* mouse neuroblastoma assay (N2a-MTT), suggesting that it has qualitatively similar sodium channel activity to other C-CTXs. These findings are significant and pave the way for a wide range of studies that were previously not possible.

Initial efforts focused on large-scale culturing of the strain of *G. silvae* (1602 SH-6) that was confirmed to produce C-CTX5 along with lower levels of C-CTX1, with the goal of purifying sufficient material for structural elucidation and studying the stability of the compounds. Over the time course of large-scale cul-

ture C-CTX production per cell was consistent (Fig. 2). Large-scale culturing and subsequent isolation of C-CTXs will allow structural confirmation by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and enable production of small amounts of much-needed quantitative reference materials. Progress in these aspects is vital for subsequent development and validation of *in vitro* bioassays, immunoassays and LC-MS-based methods for C-CTX analysis. Application of such methods in conjunction with previously developed sample clean-up techniques will greatly improve the tools available to the scientific community for understanding and managing the risks presented by C-CTXs in the marine food-web.

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Exploring the current and historic health of lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand

The biggest survey of current and historic lake health in Aotearoa-New Zealand is nearing completion. The ambitious Lakes380 Programme (www.lakes380.com), co-led by the Cawthron Institute and GNS Science, kicked off in 2017 with the lofty target of sampling 10% of the lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand. The project involved sampling and analysing lake water and surface sediments to understand contemporary lake health. Lake sediment cores were also collected and analysed to provide lake histories dating back more than a thousand years (prior to human arrival in Aotearoa-New Zealand).

The team recently released the results from their national-scale survey of over 300 lakes [1] and subsequent water quality modelling for all the lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand. This revealed that nationally, 45% of the lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand are estimated to be in poor or very poor health (Fig. 1). More gripping are the regional variations observed, with over 80% of lakes

in the North Island in poor health or worse, and in some regions of the country this reaches 90%. In summer, many of these lakes in poor health will experience severe cyanobacterial blooms that have the potential to produce toxins. This information can also be viewed in an online app (<https://lakes380.upshift.co.nz/>).

By studying the lake sediment cores, the team has been able to track the history of cyanobacterial blooms, showing that in most lakes this is a recent occurrence (50 years) [2]. The research indicates that this is related to land-use intensification (which can lead to nutrient enrichment through fertiliser run-off and sediment in-flows) and the introduction of non-native fish (which can dramatically alter food webs). The development and application of molecular methods to detect organisms that do not leave fossilised remains in lake sediments have been invaluable in this endeavour. In some cases, teasing out the drivers of lake health degradation

has only been possible through weaving together paleoecological studies of lake sediment cores with additional pieces of information such as Indigenous knowledge [3] or data on algal ecological niches [4]. Despite the challenges, proper understanding of the key drivers of degradation are critical for guiding effective restoration strategies.

Another significant focus of the project was working with Māori (the Indigenous people of Aotearoa-New Zealand) to understand more about the relationships they have with their lakes and to further empower them in their lake restoration aspirations. A digital story platform was created to document and share these experiences (<https://www.lakestoriesnz.org/>). The team also developed a virtual reality platform to transport people to a remote lake in the top of the South Island (Lake Moawhiti) and allows them to travel backwards and forwards in time (<https://lakes380.com/he-reo-no-te-puehu/>). Through this medium, people can see how changes in the landscape surrounding the lake have impacted the water quality and the creatures and plants that live in it. The virtual reality platform was co-designed with Ngāti Koata – the iwi (tribe) who have territorial rights for Lake Moawhiti and a long

Fig. 1. Data from 'Our lakes' health: past, present, future' – www.lakes380.com

Virtual reality example - Lake Moawhitu (Rangitoto ki te Tonga/d'Urville Island)

Examples from a three-dimensional virtual reality platform created in 'Our lakes' health: past, present, future' in partnership with Ngāti Koata and Department of Conservation. www.lakes380.com/he-reo-no-te-puehu/

history with the lake – allowing their knowledge and history to be woven into the experience, and their restoration vision for the lake to be communicated with their people.

The Lakes380 Programme has provided a strong foundation of knowledge on the current condition and history of lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand. The team is now shifting their focus to revitalising lakes in Aotearoa-New Zealand, through the development and implementation of holistic approaches to ensure that resources are efficiently targeted. This will require the development of new tools that can guide effective lake restoration, and strategies to engage communities in the multi-gen-

erational journey to rejuvenate the precious lake ecosystems in their regions.

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Expansion of the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM)

The CICCM is housed at the Cawthron Institute in Nelson, Aotearoa New Zealand, and in recent years has seen an increase in the number of sub-tropical species maintained [1]. The curated collection (Fig. 1) is partly government funded (through the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment) and partly funded by the Cawthron Institute.

Since the last article in HANews [2], the collection has increased to nearly 700 isolates, half of which are cyanobacteria and which are cryopreserved. In the last two years the regions represented have expanded to include polar diatoms and dinoflagellates (in particular *Polarella*) from Antarctica. Diatom species have also been isolated from sea ice brine, seawater, and samples collected from the sea ice/platelet interface. Doctoral student Jacqui Stuart travelled to Antarctica to collect these samples for a portion the 2022 Science field season with funding from the Antarctica New Zealand Sir Robin Irvine Doctoral Scholarship program. During her time in Antarctica Jacqui also assisted with work from two research projects, one led by NIWA scientist Dr. Natalie Robinson in collaboration with Prof. Ken Ryan from Victoria University of Wellington (VUW) assessing the sub-ice platelet ice using novel sampling equipment developed at NIWA. The second research project was led by Dr Andrew Martin (VUW) and Prof Ken Ryan (VUW) investigating light sensitive bacterial communities within sea ice. During the field season time was set aside for Jacqui to collect live microalgal samples from multiple sites with different ice conditions. These isolates will be used to understand the impact of changing environmental conditions on these species, and assess how this may influence the ecosystems that rely on them. The 2022 Antarctic field season was exceptionally challenging with the late development of sea ice and harsh weather causing snap freezing of some of the sampling equipment. Even with these challenging conditions Jacqui thoroughly enjoyed her experience and feels exceptionally privileged to have camped on sea ice, seen the last sunset of the season and stood in the shadow of Mt Erebus, a truly humbling and life changing adventure.

To make enquiries about microalgae in the CICCM contact Sarah Challenger through the Cawthron Institute website: <https://www.cawthron.org.nz> > ciccm.

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Fig. 1. Curation of the CICCM is carried out by (from left) Sarah Challenger, Lucy Thompson and Krystyna Ponikla.

Fig. 2. Expedition to Antarctica, 2022. Top: Jacqui Stuart on the ice (image J. Stuart); Bottom: Jacqui Stuart and Prof Ken Ryan measuring the thickness of the ice (image: Svenja Halfta, NIWA).

The Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography (ASLO) held its annual meeting from 4 – 9 June 2023 in Palma de Mallorca, Spain. ASLO 2023, the first post-covid in-person ASLO meeting in Europe, under the general theme “Resilience and Recovery in Aquatic Systems”, drew around 2400 attendees from 72 countries.

Harmful algal blooms, with six theme sessions, had a strong presence. Topics included mechanisms of HAB development; advances in monitoring

and mitigation with better prediction (improved models) or direct treatment to eliminate the toxic cells; and a good component of next generation tools used to answer questions that were so far unapproachable. In this HAN issue we present the highlights of two successful sessions. One of these sessions was dedicated to the “Mixoplankton”, the new term used to define planktonic

protists conventionally considered as “phytoplankton”, which can trap live food like a micro-zooplanktonic organisms. The other session focused on dinoflagellates of the genus *Karenia*, in particular *K. brevis* the agent of multiple noxious effects in the Gulf of Mexico.

The editors

The Mixoplankton Paradigm in Plankton Ecology

The past decade has seen the recognition of diverse plankton functional groups in marine ecology, beyond the classical phyto- and zooplankton. The mixoplankton paradigm overturns the traditional idea that all plankton can be analogized as “little plants” (phytoplankton) or “little animals” (zooplankton). In reality, many, perhaps most, planktonic organisms have the metabolic capability of synergistically employing both phototrophy and phagotrophy; because of this mixed trophic mode, they have been dubbed “mixoplankton”. The base of the marine food web is thus not as traditional science describes, raising profound questions about how we project climate change and allied anthropogenic events in reshaping the marine ecosystem and thence how we manage resources. To address such challenges, *SCOR Working Group 165 – ‘MixONET’* was recently formed. This ASLO session (Mixoplankton: The New Paradigm Testing the Resilience of Our Science in the UN Ocean Decade), consisting of *12 oral and 1 poster presentations*, focused on the overarching aspiration of MixONET to extend the mixoplankton paradigm beyond blue-sky research to real-life applications such as environmental monitoring, management, policy making, and education (Fig. 1).

Mixotrophy, as the coupling of photo-osmo-mixotrophy (i.e. photo-synthetic organisms that also take up

dissolved organic matter such as vitamins, urea, amino acids, etc.), has been researched within microalgae, and especially associated with Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) events, for decades. The new mixoplankton paradigm incorporates into the food web those protist plankton that engage in photo-osmo-phago-mixotrophy, using uptake of particles to supplement their nutritional needs. In the contexts of autecology and community ecology, there are major differences between the photo-osmo-mixotrophic (i.e. phytoplankton such as diatoms) and the photo-osmo-phago-mixotrophic (i.e. mixoplankton) microalgae (talk by **Aditee Mitra**; “Mixotroph or mixoplankton: what’s in a name?”). Mixoplankton actively hunt, kill and eat, thus acquiring nutrients and directly impacting trophic dynamics through removal of prey/competitors.

Various exemplar protistan ‘phytoplankton’ and ‘zooplankton’ species such as the food web supporting *Tripos* and *Strombidium* species, the ecosystem disruptive bloom forming green *Noctiluca scintillans*, and the HAB forming species within the *Alexandrium*, *Prorocentrum*, *Dinophysis*, and *Prymnesium* genera, are all mixoplankton (**Luciana Santoferrara**; “Global distribution of marine mixoplankton based on morphological observations and metabarcoding”). Some mixoplankters (e.g., *Alexandrium*) have their own chloroplasts while others need to acquire phototro-

phic capability by retaining plastids from ingested prey items (e.g., *Dinophysis*) or by hosting symbiotic phototrophs (e.g., green *Noctiluca*). Tracking mixoplankton distributions, spatially and temporally, based on morphological identifications or DNA sequences is now facilitated by the recently launched *Mixoplankton Database (MDB)*. The MDB is currently being cross-referenced with the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List database of over 200 HAB species to create a reference for the many HABs that are mixoplankton. Importantly for science, in moving away from a plant-animal dichotomy in marine ecology the term mixoplankton provides concise clarity. The MDB provides a tool for us to redefine the core underpinning of marine science, to perform keyword searches, to differentiate database entries, model descriptions, and to reflect the biogeochemical and ecological consequences.

Outputs from climate change models underpin various environmental management policies. Yet, climate change models are still based on the outdated phytoplankton-zooplankton dichotomy while HAB events are typically predicted using modelling frameworks that focus on physics rather than biological interactions. Mixoplanktonic activities would be expected to have far reaching impact on higher trophic levels and thence ecosystem services. Many efforts are underway to understand these

Fig. 1. Oral communications presented at the ASLO-2023 Session SS018 on Mixoplankton in Plankton Ecology.

trophic interactions and incorporate them into models of aquatic food webs. The importance of light and nutrient availability in mixoplankton succession and thence in ecosystem structure and functioning has been shown using a substantial dataset from 98 freshwater tropical lakes (Mariana Costa; “Ecosystem size drives patterns and control mechanisms of mixotrophs success across tropical lakes: A large-scale assessment of the grand écart hypothesis”). Incorporation of functional diversity of protists under the mixoplankton paradigm within 3D coupled biogeochemical models has provided a better understanding of the impact of environmental stressors on plankton trophic dynamics in a regional bay off the UK coast with aquaculture facilities (Molly James; “Addressing the challenges of modelling ecosystem services in 3D under the mixoplankton paradigm”).

Various studies have shown the importance of considering impact of environmental stressors on the ecophysiology of mixoplankton and consequent implications for the overall plankton community structure and

higher trophic levels. For example, laboratory experiments suggest that the “fish-killer” *Prymnesium parvum* could have a higher feeding efficiency when provided particulate matter compared to live prey (Clémence Boucher; “Mixotrophic growth of the ichthyotoxic Golden algae, *Prymnesium parvum*, under different sources of phosphorus”). Species of the cosmopolitan genus *Prorocentrum* have been shown to use a remarkable feeding strategy by crafting globular mucus traps of up to 120 µm diameter to capture and immobilize potential prey ranging from bacteria to *Teleaulax* (Urban Tillmann; “Mucus trap assisted mixoplanktonic activity in *Prorocentrum*”) (Fig. 2).

Dinophysis spp. is a globally ubiquitous genus that produces lipophilic toxins resulting in diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) events and closures of shellfisheries. However, current protocols in monitoring programmes are poorly designed to sample these low density non-constitutive mixotrophs, and very often their ciliate prey organisms are destroyed with fixative or mechanical damage. (Beatriz Reguera;

“Key parameters and procedures to improve monitoring and forecasting of a rare and specialized protist - *Dinophysis* species”). Acquired phototrophy in *Dinophysis* spp. is supported by plastids from the *Teleaulax/Plagioselmis* cryptophyte clade. However, due to mis-match in size, *Dinophysis* cannot capture cryptophyte cells directly but retains chloroplasts from its prey, the ciliate *Mesodinium* spp., which also retains cryptophyte plastids. While the plastids remain active in *Dinophysis*, its control of their division and function is limited. Due to the deleterious impact of *Dinophysis* blooms on ecosystem services, the transfer of functional chloroplasts within the cryptophyte-*Mesodinium*-*Dinophysis* complex has been the basis of various studies. More recent studies have focused on the impact of climate change and environmental stressors on this complex. Laboratory studies suggest that changes in ocean carbonate chemistry would not have any significant effect on the cryptophyte or *Mesodinium* spp. (Per Juel Hansen; The combined effect of pH and dissolved inorganic carbon concentrations on

Fig. 2. Suggested sequence of events leading to the formation of the mucus trap by *Prorocentrum pervagatum*. (A) Solitary cells (cell length ca. 13µm) swim in a spiralling style, releasing mucus from the large pores. (B–D) Under certain conditions, most likely of very low turbulence, the spiral swimming style coupled with random changes in direction lead to a process of mucus deposition and physical pushing by the *Prorocentrum* cell that leads to the formation of a hollow mucus ball. As the mucus ball takes shape other particles, and notably motile potential prey, become stuck to the outside surface. Towards completion of the trap, with the *Prorocentrum* now located within the hollow ball near one of the few remaining openings, the continuing rotational swimming of the dinoflagellate draws water and particles in through the large opening (a “rotating position”), with water exiting through the porous mucus walls, leaving particles trapped on the inside of mucus ball. Trapped prey are immobilized by a combination of chemical (allelochemical) and physical (mucus threads) means, and may then be consumed (E). When the trap is vacated, the decaying remnants then sink, while the *Prorocentrum* builds another trap. Image from [1]

the plastidic ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* and its cryptophyte prey). However, low light levels of different wavelengths are expected to alter the competitive advantage in the ability to acquire and maintain plastids by *Mesodinium* and *Dinophysis*. Promising results with last generation transcriptomic tools showed differences in nuclear encoded genes in *D. ovum* controlling the synthesis of phycoerythrins. This difference enables *D. ovum* to photoadapt and may prove useful to prepare molecular probes against the two species (**Sarah Garric**; “Photoacclimation of Cryptophyte plastids of *Plagioselmis prolunga* in their hosts *Mesodinium rubrum* and *Dinophysis acuminata*”). In contrast, *Strombidium rassoulzadegani*, another non-constitutive mixoplankton, can retain and use plastids from chlorophytes and cryptophytes, but appears to grow wholly heterotrophically on dinoflagellates (poster by **George McManus**; “Laboratory studies with the model ciliate mixoplankton *Strombidium rassoulzadegani*”).

The response of the different mixoplankton species to climate change and thence prediction and detection of HAB events is a formidable challenge for scientists and managers. Methods (field, laboratory, modelling) developed for phytoplankton and zooplankton need to be adapted for mixoplankton science - where required, new methods need to be developed. For example, the widely used dilution technique was developed for studying grazing on phytoplankton by zooplankton and in its current form cannot account for mixoplanktonic activities where a single-celled organ-

ism employs photo-phago-mixotrophy synergistically (**Guilherme Ferreira**; “Acknowledging mixoplankton within dilution grazing experiments”). Laboratory studies have shown that chlorophyll, used as a proxy for phytoplankton biomass in traditional dilution experiments, is inadequate for mixoplankton and that this technique needs to be modified to consider diel feeding rhythms in the experimental design.

A methodology that has been employed successfully in monitoring the mixoplanktonic HAB *Dinophysis* and could potentially be adapted for monitoring other protist plankton is the Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) (**Lisa Campbell**; “Continuous automated imaging flow cytometry for early warning of the mixoplankton harmful algal bloom forming *Dinophysis ovum*”). The IFCB, combining flow cytometry with video technology and machine learning, can identify and enumerate not only the HAB *Dinophysis* but also its source for acquired phototrophy - the ciliate *Mesodinium*. Discrimination between different “species” of the *Dinophysis acuminata* complex, with identical ribosomal and mitochondrial gene sequences, is also crucial in monitoring programmes, in particular in regions where one of the species has a much higher toxic potential than the other (i.e. Southeast US coasts). The automated sampling program deployed at the Texas Observatory for Algal Succession Timeseries (TOAST) has enabled early detection for HAB species, especially *Dinophysis ovum*. Furthermore, these long-term data from TOAST have been integrated into a mechanistic model describing the

interactions between the mixoplanktonic *Dinophysis* predator and its prey (**James M. Fiorendino**; “Modeling the effect of prey size on *Dinophysis* bloom dynamics”). Simulations using this model framework showcase the importance of consideration of the ecology and physiology of the microalgae as well as their interactions with their prey and predators.

Given the growing interest in both HABs and mixoplankton, this session was undoubtedly a harbinger of many to come in future meetings.

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Research on *Karenia brevis* blooms in the eastern Gulf of Mexico

The widespread distribution of the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia* has significant impacts on coastal communities across the globe. Therefore, the goal of ASLO Session SS088 *Advances in Understanding, Prediction, and Monitoring of Toxic Karenia (Dinoflagellate) Blooms Around the Globe* was to highlight global research on the activity and impacts of

this toxic genus.

There were six presentations and four posters of *Karenia* research presented during Session SS088. All focused on elucidating environmental factors and microbial interactions that influence bloom longevity and the success of mitigation tactics potentially used to combat blooms. Most session

abstract submissions were focused on research related to *Karenia brevis* activity and impacts in the eastern Gulf of Mexico (GOM) (Figs. 1-2)

K. brevis blooms have occurred in the eastern GOM almost every year for at least the past century, likely much longer, and local bloom monitoring programs have collected data for nearly 50 years.

In the last 5 years, two *K. brevis* blooms have lasted longer than 12+ months, resulting in a determined focus by scientist and stakeholders to understand *Karenia* bloom dynamics in this ecologically and economically important area.

Statistical techniques demonstrated that the North Atlantic Oscillation was a regional climatic stressor that positively correlated with increased *K. brevis* bloom severity in the GOM. The associated warmer temperatures and higher precipitation may result in environmental conditions favourable for *K. brevis* bloom expansion (**Tristyn Bercel**). Rain events were shown to deliver dissolved organic matter (DOM) via urban stormwater runoff and atmospheric deposition with both stimulating *K. brevis* culture growth and have the potential to promote bloom duration (**Amanda Muni-Morgan**). Riverine estuarine systems are also known to deliver DOM, specifically humics and tannins, to the GOM. Short-term incubation experiments using DOM extracts from three Florida rivers resulted in a larger growth response when compared to controls. It is believed these compounds are supplying additional nitrogen to the bloom (**Molly Dent**). Based on historical data, cold fronts are weather events that can contribute to bloom decline, but seemingly only when multiple cold fronts occur in proximity of each other. Observations from a single meteorological cold front that decreased sea surface temperatures by 2°C showed that while cells were stressed, it did not result in bloom termination (**Chloe Manley**).

This session also included projects focused on microbial community dynamics associated with blooms. Primers were developed for the identification of both *K. brevis* and *K. mikimotoi* in recent 2021 and 2023 blooms in the GOM. In 2021, *K. mikimotoi* was found at its highest concentrations when the seawater temperature was highest (33.5°C) demonstrating that these blooms are not monospecific and intra-genus interactions need to be included in bloom dynamics models (**Sarah Klass**). To understand how an individual *Karenia* cell interacts with its microbial consortia within its own microenvironment, termed the phycosphere, a protocol is actively being developed for tandem microscope and microosmotic pipette systems to isolate the pico-to-

nanoliter volume surrounding individual cells. Subsequent DNA extraction and whole genome amplification is used to identify the taxonomy and functional composition of the phycosphere microbial community, providing information that can be used to understand what role the prokaryotic community plays in supporting the health of a single *Karenia*, and potentially their role in bloom health (**Carly Moreno**). Through isolation and characterization of thirty bacterial strains from GOM bloom seawater, there is evidence of symbiotic

and antagonistic bacterial activity. It was found bacterium *Mameliella alba* CE5 supports *K. brevis* growth while *Croceibacter atlanticus* CE21 inhibits *K. brevis* growth. Based on genome sequencing, *M. alba* may provide critical vitamins and cofactors while *C. atlanticus* may synthesize polyketide algicidal compounds. This work highlights that *Karenia* bloom health can be impacted by the bacterial community members (**Cong Fei**) (Fig. 3). GOM derived viruses were also shown to lyse *K. brevis* cultures. Metagenomic sequencing

Fig. 1. Aerial photo of 2022 *K. brevis* bloom offshore Cayo Costa Florida, USA in the eastern Gulf of Mexico. Darker water contains the bloom, the white "line" separating the different water colours is congregated dead fish as a result of brevetoxin poisoning. Image courtesy of Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission

Fig. 2. Light microscopy micrographs (400x) of Lugol's preserved *Karenia brevis* cells from the 2023 bloom. Samples collected offshore Sanibel Island, Florida, in February 2023. Image courtesy Amanda Muni-Morgan.

Fig. 3. Cong Fei presenting work on symbiotic and antagonistic bacterial interactions with *K. brevis* during ASLO 2023 Session SS088.

analysis indicates some of these marine viruses are in the giant virus phylum Nucleocytoplasmic Large dsDNA Virus that are known to only infect eukaryotes. There are currently no described viruses that use *K. brevis* directly as a host, indicating novel giant viruses may be additional microbial community members capable of influencing bloom health (Anne Booker) (Fig. 4).

The large ecological and economic impacts from *Karenia* blooms in the GOM prompts the desire for mitigation techniques. The goal of *Karenia* mitigation is to clear blooms in a way that does not hurt the local environment. Laboratory incubation experiments conducted found that curcumin was the most effective tested compound at reducing *K. brevis* photophysiology and cell counts across four strains. Clay was the second most effective tested compound at

disrupting photosynthesis by reducing quantum yield of Photosystem II and relative electron transport rate (Miah Manning). In a second mitigation study, laboratory *K. brevis* cultures were incubated with fifteen different mitigation compounds and the resulting brevetoxin concentration were measured after 48 hours. Most of the mitigation compounds resulted in either no change or an increase in the brevetoxin present in the incubation. The exception being high doses of the macroalgal species *Gracilaria lemaneiformis* that eliminated 100% of *K. brevis* cells and 61% of total brevetoxins after 48 hours (Cynthia Heil).

In conclusion, ASLO Session SS088 showcased progress in understanding *K. brevis* blooms in the eastern GOM. The research demonstrated how both environmental factors and microbial in-

Fig. 4. Anne Booker presenting efforts to find natural marine viruses capable of lysing *K. brevis* during ASLO 2023 Session SS088.

teractions influence blooms, and highlighted compounds that could be used for bloom mitigation. The resulting insights are crucial for managing bloom impact on this ecologically sensitive region.

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Second UK Harmful Algae Group Meeting - Aberdeen 2023

Linda Lawton and **Christine Edwards** from the CyanoSol Research Group at the School of Pharmacy and Life Sciences in Robert Gordon University (RGU), Aberdeen, Scotland, hosted the 2nd meeting of the UK Harmful Algae Group on 13th & 14th June 2023. They were delighted to welcome international experts from industry, academia and Government bodies who shared, discussed, and highlighted the latest developments, initiatives and strategies relating to HABs.

Guest speaker (sponsored by the Microbiology Society), **Philipp Hess**, Director Research Unit PHYTOX, IFREMER, kicked off the meeting with perspectives from the French HAB Research Network, PHYCOTOX, which was the inspiration for the formation of the UK Harmful Algae Group. The presentation also highlighted developments with emerging HABs and toxins between 2018 and 2022, including updates on brevetoxins, tetrodotoxin, ovatoxins and pinnatoxins as well as the current global status of *Dinophysis*, *Pseudo-nitzschia* and *Alexandrium*, and their associated toxins. An overview of the proposed Harmful Algal Bloom- Solutions Programme (HAB-S) from the

IOC UNESCO Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (IOC IPHAB) was also presented. **Janina Costa** from the Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC) also funded by the Microbiological Society, gave an overview of SAIC's work including a range of academic-industry related SAIC supported projects such as "Mitigating microbial hazards – eliminating HABs risks in salmon farms", a project led by RGU, partnering the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS), OTAK, Bakka Frost and Queens University Belfast.

Early warning mechanisms

Gavin Tilstone from Plymouth Marine Laboratory presented Sentinel-3 products for detecting signals of eutrophication and HABs in the French-English Channel (S-3 EUROHAB). These products were demonstrated by Tilstone in a separate workshop during the meeting and can be explored at www.s3eurohab.eu/portal/. **Peter Miller** (Plymouth Marine Laboratory) presented approaches for early warning of HAB risk using satellite ocean colour and Lagrangian particle trajectories. The pros and cons of satellite ocean colour for HABs alerts

were presented and the value of merging these datasets with particle trajectories in two case studies along the coast of England to providing improved interpretation for early warning of HAB risk. This process is now running operationally.

First year DATALAB/Marine Directorate of Scottish Government PhD student **Gary Groves** (University of Highlands and Islands (UHI)/SAMS) gave an overview of the first UK experiences using Imaging Flow CytoBot (IFCB) technology for HAB detection in active aquaculture sites in the Shetland Islands in Scotland. This technology holds great potential and the first year of the project focused on overcoming logistic and technical challenges associated with deployment.

Detection methods

Presentations on new detection methods came from **Soumya Palliyil**, Scottish Biologics Facility, University of Aberdeen who reported on the development and application of recombinant antibody fragments (scAb) for the detection of microcystins and cylindrospermopsin in water and tissue samples in ELISA or lateral flow format (Fig. 1). **Bob Hatfield** (CEFAS) presented his work on Nanopore Sequencing for "fast and dirty identification of *Alexandrium* anywhere" and delivered a workshop on this technology following the meeting.

Occurrence of HABs and toxins

Andrew Turner from CEFAS reported on recent impacts of HABs on animal health in the UK looking at the impacts of cyanotoxins on dogs and cattle and results of analysis of pelagic and benthic fish species for algal toxins. A detailed study of the common Sunstar, *Crossas-*

Fig. 1. Cyanobacterial bloom collection in Rambakan Oya reservoir, Sri Lanka for toxin testing using scAb based ELISA (photo credit Malinda Dissanayake).

ter papposus (Fig. 2), from diverse sites around the UK showed all contained PSP toxins, some as high as 12,000 µg/kg whole organism even though there was no association with phytoplankton and the toxin profiles were unique and dominated by decarbamoyl saxitoxin suggesting alternative producers, possibly symbiotic bacteria.

Eileen Bresnan from the Marine Directorate of the Scottish Government gave an overview of Scotland's changing coastal environment and implications for plankton and Harmful Algal Blooms. Results from *Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership* and work from *Oslo/Paris Commission Quality Status Report* were presented which showed widescale changes in the plankton community in UK and European waters. Data from Scottish Coastal Observatory (SCObs) highlighted changes in physical, chemical and biological properties of Scotland's coastal waters which are associated with changes in phytoplankton community structure (Fig. 3). This presentation was supported by "Harmful Algae in a Policy Context" delivered by **Martin Lilley** from the Marine Evidence team (DEFRA) discussing the need for scientists to engage with policy makers.

Mitigation

Early career scientists from the CyanoSol Research Group presented multi-

Fig. 2. The common Sunstar, *Crossaster papposus* (photo credit Karl Deane, Cefas).

ple strategies for the removal of toxic cyanobacteria. **Jane Moore** presented proof of concept data on the use of biologically enhanced biochar (BEB) from industrial waste such as coconut shells, for the destruction of *Microcystis* and microcystins, demonstrating the potential of nature-based water treatment solutions. Hydronation scholar, PhD student, **Indira Menezes** demonstrated the efficiency of UV-A irradiation for destruction of 6 strains of *Microcystis aeruginosa*. Carlos Pestana presented "A paradigm-shift in water treatment: In-reservoir UV-LED driven TiO₂ photocatalysis for the removal of cyano-

bacterial – a mesocosm study". Cyanobacteria were reduced by 85% after 7 days of treatment using TiO₂ immobilised on recycled glass beads combined with 365 nm UV-LEDs in mesocosms in a Brazilian drinking water reservoir, however experimental challenges during field work included piranhas!

In summary, the meeting covered a wide range of topics and provided an excellent opportunity for early career researchers and extensive networking during breaks with posters and a pub meal and everyone is looking forward to the next one that will be hosted by CEFAS in Weymouth in 2025.

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Fig. 3. Winter (Dec, Jan) dissolved silicate (DSi) concentrations from the Scottish Coastal Observatory monitoring sites at Loch Ewe (west coast) and Stonehaven (east coast).

Gary Jay Kirkpatrick in memoriam

On August 6th, 2023, a memorial service to celebrate the life of Gary Jay Kirkpatrick (April 13, 1952 – July 25, 2023), was held by his family, friends and colleagues in Sarasota, Florida.

Gary was an engineer, a marine scientist and an otherwise unclassifiable person of tremendous impact, deep moral purpose and radiant kindness.

Gary's life story is an extraordinary example of how the freedom of independent thought and respect for interdependent reality can combine to make a luminous whole more than the sum of its parts. He was a person who found awe, and let it change him.

Gary was one of four brothers raised in Bradfordwoods, Pennsylvania, in a creative, tight-knit family where love of animals, a sense of wonder, unmeasured curiosity and mechanical skills were encouraged and embraced.

In 1961, the sportswriter Myron Cope, known as the “voice of the Pittsburgh Steelers,” heard about a family out in Allegheny County building their own airplanes, sports cars, television sets, and go karts. The Kirkpatricks, people said, looked like a regular family: the father, Robert, who went by Kirk, had a nine-to-five; the mother, Henrietta—Heni for short—raised their four boys, George, Bob, Doug, and Gary. But they had pet raccoons, and they sold wooden bowls, and well—you just had to go see them. In the resulting feature in *This Week* magazine, “Keeping Up with the Kirkpatricks,” their house—which Kirk built himself in a single year out of fir, glass, and sandstone—is described as a “three-bedroom, umpteen-workshop lodge-type,” a place where “nothing seems to be planned, but just about everything seems to happen.”

In Cope's vision of the Kirkpatrick home, a motor gets bought, and an airplane gets built; a plump, domesticated raccoon named Specs eats a breakfast of swiss cheese and bananas, and Heni tends to hundreds of orchids. “Activity is contagious,” Kirk insists, before recounting the time Bob backed his (homemade) sports car into Kirk's (homemade) plane—but Heni thought he'd run over George—and everyone

screamed so loudly that Gary, who was playing in the woods half a mile away, thought something was horribly wrong, and came running. They laughed about it, eventually.

The article is a charming snapshot of a creative, tight knit family, during the last year that all four boys lived at home.

During high school, Gary had enrolled in the Civil Air Patrol, following in the footsteps of his father, a WWII veteran of the Air Force, and his brothers, all three of whom attended the Air Force Academy. After graduation, he joined the Air Force, serving as a fighter

pilot until a crash convinced him that life on the ground working as an electrical engineer would be safer. The change was fine with Barbara, his soulmate and wife of 49 years, who he had met when she, too, was a cadet serving in the Miami Civil Air Patrol.

After leaving the Air Force in 1980, a number of very fortunate events happened as Gary turned his attention to the future. During graduate school at North Carolina State University in 1982, he was introduced to Dan Kamykowski in the Marine, Earth and Atmospheric Science Department who later became

Fig. 1. Gary Kirkpatrick and Dan Kamykowski, 1988

Fig. 2. Gary (right) with Jim Hillier and their first Slocum glider (Mote Marine Laboratory, 2005)

his mentor. In Gary, Dan saw someone who had the skills to build the tools he would need during a promising, productive career.

For those of you who did not come to marine science until the 21st century, a bit of explanation is useful: Earlier days required a great deal of its researchers. To understand the ocean, you need physics, chemistry, and biology, and beyond that, none of the tools that you *needed* to study the ocean actually *existed*, so you also needed to have some engineer in you. In 1982, Gary had everything on that list. He was also intellectually curious, open-minded, and collaborative — a genial, calm person you wanted on your watch at sea.

The fall of 1990 found Gary at Mote Marine Laboratory in Sarasota, Florida.

And in a stroke of luck, there were no phytoplankton ecologists at Mote. Gary started his work there with a broad purview, over a wide variety of organisms, in both marine and freshwater environments. By 1992, as red tide surged along Florida's southwest coast, he narrowed his focus to the organism that would eventually be known as *Karenia brevis*, named for one of his and Barbara's co-researchers, naturalist Karen Steidinger of Florida's Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission.

At Mote, Gary developed the Breve-Buster, the first automated red-tide detector, along with the process it used to detect *K. brevis* — called fourth derivative analysis, which is now a widely-used absorption spectra classification technique. He also built SUPA, "self-con-

tained underwater photosynthesis apparatus," an algal laboratory that could be lowered into the water.

But he wasn't done yet. He developed FlowThrough CDOM, a method of measuring organic matter in waterways and, working with Robert Currier, Barb (an Ed.D. studying the human-health impacts of harmful algal blooms in her own work), Gary developed HABScope, a low-cost microscopy system that enables the Red Tide Respiratory Forecast.

Talking with Gary was freeform: We'd move from fourth derivative mathematics to hard-core cell biology to the engineering of gliders in the same conversation; his was an intense curiosity, always wanting to know more about how something worked, and why. He was humble; he wore his intelligence with modesty. He was the last person on the planet who would ever try to show up another person for being smarter, and he was never motivated by trying to be the first person with the answer. In our relationship, I was the cheerleader; Gary was the one who always wanted a little bit more data. We would toss around crazy ideas, and between that push-and-pull, that dance of enthusiasm and rigor, somehow they always seemed to get some momentum, and a lot of them became real things that people actually use.

Gary worked at Mote from 1990 to 2022, publishing more than 80 papers, raising his own money, managing his own team, and collaborating with hundreds of scientists at dozens of institutions. He was also an incredible mentor who helped to support and guide the careers of numerous students and young colleagues.

With his electrical engineering skills and understanding of both physical and environmental science, Gary was able to move beyond concepts.

He built real tools. Most importantly, Gary built our field.

Submitted by Oscar Schofield. Adapted from the eulogy written by Gary's niece, Barbara Bourland, and delivered by Oscar Schofield, at Gary's memorial service on Aug. 6, 2023. You can honor Gary by performing a random act of kindness. As a living-donor kidney transplant recipient, Gary would also encourage you to become an organ donor.

Fig. 3. Gary in a FL Red tide meeting in St Petersburg, FL 2007 talking with Jan Landsberg

Fig. 4. Gary and Oscar at the Underwater Glider Workshop 2019.

The Sherkin Island Marine Station Long-term Phytoplankton Record

HAB-related science at Sherkin Island

One clear sign of the aging process is when the editors of the IOC Newsletter *Harmful Algae News* invite you to submit “a piece” for their historical archive series. This time, the invitation coincided with the recent publication of what is arguably the most extensive phytoplankton record to date (<https://doi.org/10.15468/crt6sc> and www.sherkinmarinedata.ie). This allows me to pay tribute to some remarkable HAB-related work that started before the well-funded establishment of the active research field we enjoy today: it has been quietly soldiering on until now, unfunded, and largely under the HAB community radar.

I first became aware of this work in 1986, when the director of Sherkin Island Marine Station (SIMS), Matt Murphy, stopped by my office at the University of Oslo and asked me if it was true that I knew something about “red-tide”. I must have convinced him that there was at least some truth in that. After a brief discussion he said “if I provide round-trip airfare and accommodation for 12 scientists from anywhere in the world, could you help select them and help organize an international conference on “The problems of toxic dinoflagellates in aquaculture”? Neither of us realized that this was the start of a great enduring friendship and scientific cooperation. (Perhaps somebody told him of my highest regard for voluntary service?)

Like many of our generation, Matt and his late wife Eileen were surely inspired at least in part by Racheal Carson’s book *Silent Spring*. With no formal scientific training, they nevertheless established the Marine Station in 1975 on a little island almost at the southern tip of Ireland, and embarked on a life-time ambition to record as much as possible of the marine and terrestrial wildlife in the surrounding area and to monitor the inevitable future

changes it faced. Details of the station and its research activities including surveys of the rocky shore, terrestrial plants, birds, otters and insects may be found at www.sherkinmarine.ie.

The phytoplankton survey is unique in all its main features, on a global scale, and as with all SIMS work was funded on an extremely low budget without any government assistance, and carried out by young volunteer scientists. I believe this survey, with unusually dense sampling of the water column within a restricted coastal area over time, together with associated environmental data, arguably produced the largest and most comprehensive record to date of phytoplankton assembled from one area of the marine realm. Many researchers, and perhaps all funding agencies may be surprised by this claim – but the details speak for themselves.

The long-term phytoplankton survey

The phytoplankton programme started in response to a “red tide” event along the southwest coast of Ireland in 1978. It evolved through an initial exploratory phase, with particular focus on the toxic species threatening the local shellfishery, and the station hopes to publish data from these and subsequent toxic events at a future date if possible. However, realizing the need for long-term monitoring of the whole phytoplankton for harmful algal blooms (HAB) to be considered in their ecological context, the survey of the whole phytoplankton reported here was established. This covered 12 station (Fig. 1). Station B8, closest to the Marine Station, was designated as a reference site to be sampled most frequently (a total of 980 sampling trips between 1978 and 2014), and stations B2, B5, B6, S1, S2, S3, and S4 were established to provide core information for the long term monitoring record (1980-2014). Four additional stations were subsequently added: B3 (from 1985 onwards), B4 and B7 (from 1986), and B9 (from 1988). B3 and B7 were re-established from two sites pre-

Fig. 1. Sherkin Island. Stations surveyed

viously sampled during the initial stages of the survey and records from those early years are included in the dataset.

The survey aimed to sample stations approximately every 12 days, subject to weather conditions, between April and October each year. Discrete water samples were taken by Nansen bottle for analysis at depth intervals of 0, 2.5, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 50m where water depths permitted at each station. When possible, a vertical plankton net haul was taken at all stations to cover the water column between the sampled depths. Water temperature and salinity were recorded for each sample, and Secchi disc readings were taken for estimating water transparency at each station.

The dataset includes standardized phytoplankton counts of all identifiable species together with recorded location, date, water depth, water temperature, salinity, conductivity, Secchi disc estimate, tide height at time of sampling, sea conditions and weather conditions. Standard air temperature records from the nearby manual weather station at Sherkin Island Marine Station covering the same time period offer comparisons with the marine records for climate-related studies (Met Éireann : The Irish Meteorological Service (online) c.2021 [accessed 2021 Sept 17] <https://www.met.ie/climate/available-data/historical-data>).

In all, the unique dataset presented here comprises a long-term record from 1980 to 2014 encompassing over 34,000 samples and at least 440,000 counts of individual phytoplankton species, together with over 34,400 seawater temperatures, and 28,000 salinity measurements. Over 350 phytoplankton taxa were recorded, identified to species where possible with reference to literature available at that time. Anyone who has successfully applied for a project to carry out the equivalent of even any small part of this programme will appreciate this amazing achievement. It is interesting (to say the least!) to attempt to guess what the cost might be to carry out such a programme through the established science funding systems. A “back of an envelope calculation” would quickly suggest millions of dollars – unrealistic, and beyond the most ambitious scientist’s imagination for a grant proposal. Nevertheless,

these results show a level of complexity in natural variation that challenges our ability to separate this from the humanly-induced environmental damage everyone is concerned about (Dale & Murphy 2014). Can we know what is happening out in the ocean without detailed monitoring? It strengthens my belief that an annual budget on the order of that NASA and all the other countries spend on space exploration is needed if we are to really understand the oceans and their environmental problems. If that is impossible, then at least it should be recognized, and publicized.

Other HAB-related activities at Sherkin Island – International Conferences

1st International Conference/workshop on The Problems of Toxic dinoflagellate Blooms in Aquaculture

At the time of writing, the HAB community is looking forward to celebrating the 20th International HAB Conference, to be held in Japan in 2023, and it is interesting for me to reflect on the year of the first of these meetings, also in Japan, in 1987. I was not able to attend that meeting, but 1987 stands out in my memory, as I am sure it does for others who were there, as the year of the 1st Sherkin International Conference/workshop: *The Problems of Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms in Aquaculture*, resulting from my first meeting with Matt Murphy, Director of SIMS. Matt realized the great potential for aquaculture to offer local jobs for young people in coastal Ireland who otherwise had to move away to find employment, many immigrating to other countries. HAB was emerging as the major obstacle for developing this potential. Little was known about “red tides”, and as elsewhere just the mention of such an event was enough to put consumers off all marine food. Traditional fisheries suffered economically, and insurance premiums for aquaculture start-ups were prohibitive.

We assembled a mixed group of fifteen speakers to share their science from different countries, followed by a workshop to discuss where we were with “red tides” and what was needed to progress further in understanding them. The conference was attended by

a few invited scientists other than the speakers, and was open to local politicians, fishery representatives and insurers who were interested. The speakers included a couple of oceanographers and a mixture of both established and up and coming HAB scientists. Most are now well-known contributors to the field: Dan Baden (who also presented a paper from Karen Steidinger), S. Fraga, I.R. Jenkinson, G.M. Hallegraef, T. Okaichi, Max Taylor, Alan White, and Charlie and Clarice Yentsch. Apart from the science, the highlights included the spectacular arrival by helicopter of the Minister for the Marine for the opening ceremony, and a magnificent banquet put on by the chefs from the best hotels in Cork using seafoods donated by local fisheries.

Among the recommendations from this meeting were:

1. The need for a newsletter to update scientists and aquaculturists worldwide on the outbreaks of “red tides”. This prompted SIMS to publish “The Red Tide Newsletter”, quarterly from 1988 to 1992, the forerunner for others up to today’s IOC (UNESCO) Harmful Algae News.
2. The need to maintain training for phytoplankton taxonomists – at that time seemingly a “dying breed”. The International Phytoplankton Training Course run from the University of Oslo, Norway, was facing an uncertain future at the time. Henrik and his Copenhagen team have certainly answered that call well!
3. The need to bring “red tide” scientists, aquaculturists, insurers and local politicians together to help resolve start-up difficulties for this emerging industry. Including local politicians proved particularly valuable – they asked pertinent questions one does not normally expect in scientific discussions. SIMS sent invitations to the 2nd International Conference to all the local councils in Ireland inviting them to send representatives, and many did.

2nd International Conference/workshop on The Problems of Toxic dinoflagellate Blooms in Aquaculture

The second conference, in 1989, began with a workshop on HAB species taxonomy, with the world authority on the genus *Alexandrium*, Enrique Balech from Argentina invited to share his wealth of

Fig. 2. From left: Matt Murphy, Vera L. Trainer, Enrique Balech, Karen Steidinger. Sherkin Island 1989.

experience from over 50 years studying phytoplankton worldwide. Among the other well-known HAB scientists were Karen Steidinger, Vera Trainer, Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Malte Elbrächter, and Santiago Fraga (Fig. 2). A highlight of the conference was the entrance of a horse into the lecture hall which Matt Murphy promptly grabbed by the mane to escort back outside. The main topics and discussions of the conference centered on the worldwide occurrence of HAB, and problems for aquaculture, with presentations from insurers, managers, and regulators of the aquaculture industry. To my knowledge, this was the first, and perhaps only such meeting where sci-

entists, and both fishing and insurance industries and politicians discussed HAB together?

Publishing “The Genus *Alexandrium Halim (Dinoflagellata)*” by Professor Enrique Balech

It is appropriate for me to include mention of one of the particularly noteworthy results from the second conference at a time when we mourn the recent passing of Karen Steidinger, since she was very much involved. While Prof. Enrique Balech was with us we learned that he was preparing a manuscript for a book on *Alexandrium*, but was uncertain about publication possibilities.

Matt said the Station was honoured to publish it, and Karen accepted responsibility for helping Balech complete the work. Karen, who regarded Balech as a mentor (Fig. 3), employed a Spanish translator to produce an English version from which Karen’s colleague, Beverly Roberts completed the published version. “The Genus *Alexandrium (Halim) Dinoflagellata*” by Balech is an essential reference for anyone working on *Alexandrium* worldwide. Both Karen and Matt wrote moving tributes to Balech in the book, and Matt said that publishing this great man’s work and making it available to the scientific world was a privilege for the Station. A limited number of copies are available for purchase from SIMS at 40 Euros inclusive postage, and here I wish to acknowledge the generous spirit of a German colleague who willingly bid twice that much at an ISSHA conference auction.

Concluding remarks

I hope this little view into SIMS work will inspire others. Some of the young volunteers gained invaluable experience that helped them on to a career in our science, and readers will recognize some well-known HAB researchers among the list of volunteers in the background information to the published survey data. There is still a pool of young, well qualified students without relevant job opportunities who could benefit from the sort of chance that SIMS offered, and it is questionable if an alternative way can be found to producing sorely needed adequate long-term data. Unfortunately, SIMS could not continue the phytoplankton survey after 2014, but I could wish that someone somewhere could take up the challenge. Maybe some philanthropic foundation, or even a funding agency willing to think outside the box could be persuaded to raise a little seed money to start such an effort?

Fig. 3. Enrique Balech and Karen Steidinger. Sherkin Island 1989. Photo by Santiago Fraga

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Get Ready for the Upcoming ICHA20 meeting

The ICHA meeting, 5-10 November in Hiroshima Japan (<https://icha2023.org>) is nearly here. For those of you who are attending, please remember to book your room and register for the Wednesday afternoon excursions and the Gala dinner. There are still a variety of accommodations available to choose from. The afternoon excursions include Iwakuni City located in Yamaguchi Prefecture featured the renown Kintaikyo Bridge and the restored Iwakuni Castle; trip to Kumano brush, one of Hiroshima's traditional craft of brush making; a visit to Saijo one of the three most famous Sake brewing areas in Japan; visit to scenic port town of Onomichi noted for its scenic beauty, old temples and seasonal flowers; and the shrine Island of Miyajima, a world heritage site with Itsukushima-Jinja Shrine, Misen Mountain and friendly deer.

Prior to the Gala dinner, people will gather at Grand Prince Hotel, for a pre-party at the "Hiroshima Gokoku Shrine", located near Hiroshima Castle. Here, light refreshments and welcome drinks will be served, and participants

will enjoy a samurai performance and ken-dama. Afterwards, participants will move to "Hotel Granvia Hiroshima", the main venue for the dinner near JR Hiroshima Station, where they will enjoy a seated buffet-style dinner and enjoy "Kagura", a traditional performing art of Hiroshima. For those brave souls who wish, following the Gala dinner, there will be an optimal drinking session in "Nagarekawa", the famous downtown area of drinkers' heaven in Hiroshima City where the participants will enjoy a variety of establishments.

ISSHA Auction

This meeting will also see the resumption of the long tradition of holding an auction to raise funds to support stu-

dent travel to the next conference. This is a great way to spend time with colleagues and having fun bid on interesting and fun items. To further contribute to the festivities, drinks will be available for purchase. Items can include pottery, games, toys, liquors, clothes, books, etc. All proceeds go to supporting student travel for the next conference. If you plan on donating an item, please send a picture (jpg or png preferable) and a short description to the following email address, preferably several weeks or more ahead of the meeting. This information will be used to produce a slideshow of auction items. You can drop donated items off at the information booth adjacent to the reception area upon your arrival at the venue. Alternatively, if you ship them ahead of time, kindly utilize the address below for shipping purposes. We kindly request that you forward an email to the designated contact person to ensure a streamlined process. This email should include your name, shipping address, and pertinent item details. Also, to exempt import tax, please mention on the shipping invoice that the item is "gift", and the estimated value of the item should be less than 10000 JPY (For items more than this value, please at first contact us by email).

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Looking forward to seeing you at the auction on November 9th from 19:30 at the room Setouchi 1 & 2.

Once the meeting concludes, a summary of the meeting will be published in HAN. We hope to see you at the meeting.

*Wayne Litaker (ISSHA President)
Ichiro Imai (Chair), and Toshiyuki Suzuki, and Satoshi Nagai, Members of the Local Organizing Committee*

Top: Hiroshima Gokoku Shrine

Bottom: Kagura, a traditional Hiroshima performing art

Announcement for a forthcoming Special Issue of the newsletter dedicated to the life and work of Karen Steidinger

As an admiring early colleague of Karen, I was asked to help announce the editors' intention to produce a Special Issue celebrating her wonderful legacy. There was such a warm spontaneous response from so many people as word spread of her passing: ex colleagues or students in international taxonomy courses in Europe, American close colleagues or simply people knowing her work and loving her personality. Karen's closest colleagues held a very moving tribute to her in Florida on September 9th, and the editors wish to follow this with a Special Issue marking the respect and admiration for Karen held by the broad international HAB community and ISSHA membership. Publication date will be announced later,

and in the meantime a long-serving ISSHA member and ex-President (2004-2008), Pat Tester – in collaboration with Jane Landsberg, has accepted the invitation to assemble written contributions and photos and be Guest Editor for the proposed Special Issue. I look forward to the Special Issue – I am sure the ISSHA community will produce a worthy tribute to one of its earliest pioneers.

Barrie Dale, University of Oslo, Norway

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

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